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The hardest places to eliminate: where, why, and how

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The hardest places to eliminate: where, why, and how

1. Introduction

In an earlier analysis, presented in [Chapter XX](#), an evaluation was undertaken of possible future trends in malaria transmission to the year 2050, taking into account the effects of large-scale changes in the global environment (including those related to population growth, climate change, socio-economic development, infrastructure, land cover change etc), along with the potential additional impact of increasing malaria control intensity. One key outcome was the identification of areas in which malaria elimination in sub-Saharan Africa may be most challenging – with transmission predicted to continue in 2050 even under optimistic scenarios of malaria intervention coverage with existing tools with continued high efficacy, and with the addition of possible new drug and vaccine-based strategies. In this Chapter we present a series of new analyses that build on this work. In particular, we aim to understand those factors that are most important in determining the hardest places to eliminate and point to potential strategies to mitigate these factors and facilitate eradication. We present a series of analyses that address the following questions. (i) What is the detailed geographic distribution of areas predicted to remain endemic by 2050, which countries are projected to eliminate, which will not, and which will house the most significant areas of transmission? (ii) How do different global environmental trends, for example climate-related versus socio-economic, influence the likelihood of elimination in a given location? (iii) How do transmission characteristics (underlying receptivity, *Anopheles* bionomics etc) and global environmental trends interact to determine the likelihood of elimination in a given location? (iv) Given the above characterisations of the projected hardest places, how might further enhancement of malaria control not yet considered, in particular measures to tackle outside biting, potentially impact residual pockets of transmission?

2. Methods

Detailed geographical description of the 'hardest places'

The earlier analysis presented in [Chapter XX](#) includes various projections of the landscape of transmission in sub-Saharan Africa in 2050 under different future scenarios. One such projection evaluates a scenario in which the effects of plausible global environmental trends are combined with aggressive scale-up of current malaria control interventions (specifically such that ITNS, IRS and ACTs are deployed to reach 80% effective coverage with continued high efficacy), and the analysis identifies areas likely to be able to eliminate local malaria transmission under those conditions versus those that

will not (see Chapter XX, Figure 4D). Here, we have taken this projected map and computed summary statistics for each of the currently endemic countries in sub-Saharan Africa that highlight the primary foci of transmission remaining in 2050. Specifically, we compute for each country (i) the area (km²) projected to have ongoing transmission; (ii) that area as a percentage of the country; (iii) the 2050 population living in areas with ongoing transmission; (iv) that population as a percentage of the national population.

Decomposition of global trend drivers of ongoing transmission

A key determinant of the future trajectory of malaria in a given location is the impact of global environmental trends. Chapter XX describes in detail how many aspects of future environmental change were captured using gridded spatial data linked to the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway/Representative Concentration Pathway (SSP/RCP) framework for future scenario analysis developed under the auspices of the United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). In that preceding analysis, these future-projected data were used in a Bayesian geostatistical model that was able to characterise their multidimensional relationship with data on malaria endemicity (*Plasmodium falciparum* parasite rate, *PfPR*) and, thus, predict the combined impact of these global trends on future malaria transmission. These global trends include a wide range of very different aspects of the natural and human environment, and the direction and magnitude of their impact on malaria is equally diverse. Identifying the different impacts on malaria associated with different types of environmental change was not a focus of the earlier analysis but is important in the context of better understanding why some areas are projected to eliminate and some are not, and to potentially identify mitigation strategies where these trends hinder progress to elimination. Here we have undertaken a decomposition analysis in order to quantify the distinct effects of different categories of environmental change. Trends were categorized as: (i) socio-economic trends (which included changes in night-time light brightness, % houses electrified, % housing with modern construction, % impervious surfaces, population density, Gross domestic product (pixel level) and % urban population); (ii) landcover trends (which included changes to % forested primary land, % non-forested primary land, % managed pasture, % irrigated land, and deforestation); (iii) vegetation density trends, which was preferred over measures of precipitation because it is more closely coupled with malaria transmission; and (iv) temperature trends. For each of the four categories, the original geostatistical model was run to predict *PfPR* in 2050 with projected changes to those environmental characteristics included but with all other factors (the other three environmental trend categories and malaria control interventions) held constant at 2017 levels. This generated projections of 2050 in which the only drivers of change were the trends within each category. The resulting maps of *PfPR* in 2050 were then converted into maps showing absolute change in *PfPR* between 2017 and 2050. As a

further summary, the average value of change was computed for each country, and displayed via simple barplots for comparison.

Analysing relative roles of transmission characteristics and environmental trends in determining elimination

In the analytical framework developed in Chapter XX, three factors combine to determine the level of transmission in 2050 and whether elimination is projected to be achieved or not. First, the level of receptivity, which is defined here as the inherent propensity of each location to support transmission – i.e. in the absence of any significant malaria control efforts. This was approximated in the analysis using levels of *PfPR* estimated for the year 2000 on the basis that coverage with ITNs and ACTs was close to zero in that year. This is not a perfect proxy for receptivity, since it ignores any IRS activity in that year and that other (non- ACT) antimalarials retained a degree of efficacy at that time, but it is likely to nevertheless approximate conditions if current modern interventions were withdrawn. Second, the combined impact of the environmental trends, described in the previous section. Third, the bionomics characteristics of locally important *Anopheles* vectors. These are important because aspects such as the fraction of bites that occur indoors (endophily) and on humans (anthropophily) potentially mediate the impact achieved by the aggressive scaling of ITNs and IRS, which are targeted towards indoor biting. In any given location, these three factors will interact in complex ways to determine the likelihood of elimination under specified levels of malaria control. To explore the relative importance of each factor their statistical distributions, summarised using boxplots, were compared in areas projected by 2050 to eliminate versus not.

Evaluation of requirements to eliminate from hardest places

As discussed, the analysis in Chapter XX included a projection of transmission under a scenario of aggressive scaling of current interventions with presumed continued high efficacy and, additionally, scenarios with the additional deployment of some prospective new tools: monoclonal antibody-based vaccine; a pre-erythrocytic vaccine; treatment with Dihydroartemesinin+piperazine as a replacement for existing ACTs; and a transmission blocking vaccine (see Chapter XX, Figure 5). While each of these new tools were modelled as yielding further impacts on pockets of remaining transmission in 2050, none led to the complete cessation of transmission across the continent as a whole. This suggests that, under a scenario where 80% of clinical malaria cases are receiving prompt access to ACTs, the additional impact of adding further drug and vaccine-based tools is likely to be modest. Conversely, there may be considerable scope for further reducing transmission by targeting mosquitoes outside the home, because the modelled scenarios only included vector control measures (ITNs and IRS) that target mosquitoes during indoor biting/resting. To evaluate this further, we built

on the mechanistic modelling analysis presented in [Chapter XX](#), which utilised the EMoD model framework, to consider the impact of significant deployment of Attractive Toxic Sugar Bait (ATSB) in addition to ITNs, IRS and ACTS at 80% effective coverage. In EMoD, the impact of ATSBs is controlled by varying coverage (defined as the percentage of sugar feeding mosquitoes in locations proximal to an ATSB), the initial killing rate (the percentage of those mosquitoes killed by the trap), the duration of efficacy of a deployed ATSB, and the number and timing of deployments across a year. These different factors were combined to yield a single metric - the kill rate – which specifies the overall annual percentage of sugar-feeding mosquitoes killed by ATSBs in a location. Four levels of kill rate were evaluated to reflect progressively more aggressive levels of deployment: 0.15%, 3%, 15% and 30%.

3. Results

Detailed geographical description of ‘hardest places’

[Figure 1](#) shows the results of the analysis to characterise, country by country, the extent of projected ongoing transmission in 2050 given global environmental change and aggressive scaling of currently available malaria control tools. In 2017, Africa experiences endemic transmission across 23 million km² in which area 1.63 billion people are projected to live by 2050. Under the modelled scenario, transmission in 2050 is sustained in pockets distributed across the continent totalling 609,000 km² and housing 99.6 million people. The country with the largest combined area with ongoing transmission is Mozambique (164,000 km²), and five countries (Mozambique, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Cote d’Ivoire, and Tanzania) together account for two-thirds (66%) of the total area with ongoing transmission. A total of 26 countries are projected to have either eliminated altogether or to harbour transmission in less than one percent of their land area. In population terms, Nigeria is projected to house the largest population at risk of ongoing transmission in 2050 at 49.8 million, which represents almost exactly half of the total at risk across the continent. Other countries in the top five by population at risk are Mozambique, Tanzania, Burkina Faso and Malawi. As well as the absolute area with ongoing transmission in each country, it is also useful to consider the within-country fraction these areas represent: small countries may contribute little to the continental total but nevertheless have proportionally large problems from their national perspective. Four countries are projected to retain transmission in at least 10% of their area (Burundi, Mozambique, Malawi, Cote d’Ivoire) with the largest fraction in Burundi of nearly one-third (32%) of its area.

Decomposition of global trend drivers of ongoing transmission

[Figure 2](#) shows the mapped results of the analysis to decompose the combined impacts of environmental change into the distinct categories of environmental characteristics. [Figure 3](#) shows

the same outputs summarised at national level. For reference, Panel A on both Figures shows the results for the combined impacts, with projected decreases in *PfPR* due to environmental trends shown in red shades and increases in green shades. These combined effects yield declines in most parts of Africa, including large declines of over 25 percentage points in western and central African countries (Sierra Leone, Burkina Faso, Togo, Guinea, Cameroon, Equatorial Guinea, Benin and DRC). Of the 43 endemic African countries considered, the combined environmental trends yielded mean declines in 32, and mean increases in the remaining 11. Two countries (Ethiopia and Rwanda) had projected increases in excess of three percentage points (4.7% and 6.9% respectively). [Figure 2B](#) and [Figure 3B](#) show equivalent results when only socioeconomic trends are considered. These are projected to yield almost universal declines in *PfPR*, with particular foci of impact in West Africa (Sierra Leone, Burkina Faso, Guinea, Togo) as well as parts of DRC, Uganda and Cameroon. [Figure 2C](#) and [Figure 3C](#) show results for landcover trends, which demonstrate a more mixed impact. Areas associated with projected forest loss, in particular around the Congo Basin in northern DRC, Central Africa Republic, and Cameroon, are projected to have declining *PfPR*, whereas substantial areas of Kenya, Ethiopia and South Sudan in East Africa, and of Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, and Senegal in West Africa experience increases in *PfPR*. These are likely linked to the projected increases in cultivated land in these areas (captured by projected increases in managed pasture, crops and irrigated land). Panels D and E on [Figures 2 and 3](#) show results for trends in vegetation density and temperature, respectively. These projected trends both have an overall but not universal tendency to reduce *PfPR* (mean declines in 28 and 27 countries, respectively, versus mean increases in 15 and 16 countries). In general, the predicted direction and magnitude of these climate-related trends are more geographically heterogeneous than other trends, with many countries displaying fragmented patterns of both increase and decrease.

Analysing relative roles of transmission characteristics and environmental trends in determining elimination

[Figure 4](#) shows the results of the analysis to compare the relative importance of transmission characteristics and environmental trends in determining whether elimination is projected to occur in a given location by 2050 under high coverage of ITNs, IRS and ACTs. Each panel shows a simple boxplot that summarises the statistical distribution of one of the four factors considered and how that distribution differs between places that were subsequently projected to eliminate versus not. As can be seen, the level of receptivity ([Figure 4A](#)) is the factor which differs most starkly between eliminating and non-eliminating areas, with mean receptivity in eliminated areas (*PfPR* of 26.1%) being less than half that in non-eliminating areas (*PfPR* of 61.1%). The impact of global trends differed much less ([Figure 4B](#)), with mean impact in eliminated areas (- 4.2% *PfPR* between 2017 and 2050) only

marginally more negative than in non-eliminated areas (-0.6%), although the distribution as a whole was substantially more negative (25th percentile of -19.2% *PfPR* in eliminated areas versus -8.2% *PfPR* in non-eliminated). Endophily (Figure 4C) showed no clear differential, with an identical mean of 55.6% of bites occurring indoors in both eliminated and non-eliminated areas. Anthropophily (Figure 4D) was also not meaningfully different, with a mean of 76% of bites occurring on humans in areas projected to eliminate versus 75% in non-eliminated areas.

Evaluation of requirements to eliminate from hardest places

Figure 5 shows the results of the modelling analysis to evaluate the likely impact of widespread deployment of ATSBs in addition to 80% effective coverage of ITNs, IRS and ACTs. At kill rates of 0.15% (Panels A and B) and 3% (Panels C and D), the additional impact of adding ATSBs in the remaining pockets of transmission is minimal. However, at much higher kill rates, impact becomes significant. Deployment of ATSBs at a 15% kill rate in projected 2050 conditions leads to elimination of malaria from Africa in all but a very small handful of locations (Panel F) and kill rates of 25% achieve total elimination in both 2030 and 2050 projections (Panels G and H).

4. Discussion

In this analysis we have built on preceding work to better understand the individual and combined roles of different characteristics of malaria transmission and of future environmental trends in determining the likelihood of elimination under various scenarios of intervention deployment.

Among global environmental trends, the strongest drivers of declining *PfPR* are likely to be socioeconomic factors, capturing impact of urbanisation, improved infrastructure, improved housing and so on. These result in significant projected declines in many places, but the magnitude of impact will depend both on current levels of economic development and infrastructure (with countries already further along this trajectory having less capacity to improve) and their forecasted trajectory of increase to 2050. Projected changes in landcover are likely to have much more varied impacts, with deforestation in the Congo basin likely reducing transmission while intensification of agriculture and irrigation in east and west Africa having a detrimental impact. This highlights the need for vigilance and ongoing surveillance as large scale changes in land use and/or landcover occur in Africa in coming decades, and the potential need for tailored mitigation strategies to counter the specific mechanisms by which such changes increase malaria risk. Climate impacts are, overall, projected to be more modest than socioeconomic or landcover changes but may be locally significant in many locations. This geographic variability, coupled with the inherently uncertain nature of the climatic projections, points again to the need for enhanced networks to monitor, or predict, local changes to climate and

its possible implications for malaria elimination, as well as sensitive surveillance systems to capture fluctuations in malaria incidence.

Despite the complexity of untangling the relative importance of receptivity, global trends, and local *anopheles* bionomics in determining whether a location is likely to eliminate or not, the results shown here were nevertheless unambiguous: receptivity, or the level of underlying suitability for transmission, remains by far the biggest factor in determining the magnitude of the challenge in reaching elimination. While this is mediated by the locally varying impact of global trends, which will effectively act to alter this receptivity, our analysis suggests that the magnitude of these alterations is not such that it will fundamentally change the landscape of risk and, thus, areas with high receptivity today remain the likeliest candidates as the hardest places for future eradication. Perhaps more surprising was the apparent unimportance of levels of endophily and anthropophily. A reasonable expectation would have been that, because these should strongly mediate the impact of scaling up contemporary vector control to 80% coverage, they would play a larger role in determining where the last pockets of transmission occur. This may reflect the relative small variation in these variables across Africa or, simply, that the magnitude of variation in the overall amount of transmission (driven by receptivity) remains more important than where and on whom bites are received.

The final stage of the analysis presented here, in which the impact of adding ATSBs was evaluated, suggests that deployment of this intervention at potentially achievable levels of coverage could be adequate, alongside the very aggressive deployment of existing tools, and coupled with the generally beneficial impacts of global environmental trends, to bring the continent to the brink of elimination by 2050. It is important to note that this would not necessarily imply blanket coverage with all interventions. Achieving 80% coverage of ITNs and ACTs would yield a much reduced area with ongoing transmission, into which IRS could then be deployed, which would in turn further reduce the necessary target area for subsequent deployments of ATSBs. This progressive targeting approach, whilst clearly still representing a large increase in resources compared to present day coverage levels, would nevertheless be vastly less costly than blanket coverage.

In conclusion, changes to the human and built environment to 2050 are an important determinant of the likelihood of elimination in any given location, and socioeconomic trends appear the most important and most beneficial to malaria elimination. Impacts of land cover change and climate are mixed and local vigilance including high quality surveillance will be required to predict and mitigate against their potentially deleterious effects. Despite the important role of global trends, the largest factor in determining the hardest places to eliminate remains their inherent receptivity for transmission. In the limited regions of Africa where transmission is projected to remain in 2050 despite the combined effects of the changing environment and very high coverage of contemporary control

tools, the additional deployment of ATSBs may have substantial further impact leading to elimination in all but a tiny fraction of locations.

Figure 1. National-level summaries of area and population with ongoing transmission in 2050 under SSP2 and with malaria control maintained at current levels. Plots show national-level (A) area; (B) % of national area; (C) population and (D) % of national population with ongoing transmission.

Figure 2. Projected absolute change in *PfPR* by 2050 at pixel level. Maps show change 2017-2050 due to (A) all global environmental trends; (B) only socioeconomic trends; (C) only landcover trends; (D) only vegetation trends; (E) only temperature trends. All scenarios relate to SSP2 and with malaria control maintained at current levels. Dark grey areas are non-endemic in 2017.

Figure 3. Projected absolute change in *PfPR* by 2050 at national level. Barplots show change due to (A) all global environmental trends; (B) only socioeconomic trends; (C) only landcover trends; (D) only vegetation trends; (E) only temperature trends. All scenarios relate to SSP2 and with malaria control maintained at current levels.

Figure 4. Boxplots comparing statistical distribution of candidate driving factors in areas projected to eliminate versus not eliminate by 2050 in a scenario with optimistic intervention coverage. Plots are shown for (A) receptivity, which was approximated using *PfPR* in the year 2000; (B) the magnitude and direction of impact (absolute change in *PfPR* 2017 to 2050) caused by combined global trends excluding changes to malaria control; (C) endophily, defined as the estimated percentage of bites by local *Anopheles* occurring indoors ; (D) anthropophily, defined as the estimated percentage of bites by local *Anopheles* on humans. Boxplots show the median (bold line), interquartile range (white box), and 2.5th-97.5th percentile (extent of whiskers).

ATSB: kill rate: 0.15%

ATSB: kill rate: 3%

ATSB: kill rate: 15%

ATSB: kill rate: 25%

Figure 5. Projected future impact on malaria endemicity of the global environmental trends, increased coverage of existing malaria control, and additional deployment of Attractive Toxic Sugar Bait (ATSBs). Maps show *Plasmodium falciparum* infection prevalence (2-10 year olds) for the years 2030 (A, C, E, G) and 2050 (B, D, F, H). All projections included enhanced coverage of existing malaria control tools (80% coverage with ITN, ACT and IRS) and additionally large-scale deployment of ATSBs at increasing levels of kill rate. See text for coverage definition. All projections relate to the SSP2 pathway.